

***Chlaenius* spp. (Coleoptera:Carabidae), a leaf folder (LF) predator**

A. T. Barrion and J. A. Litsinger,
Entomology Department, IRRRI

Chlaenius ground beetles (*C. posticalis* Motschulsky, *C. nr. circumdatus*

Chaudori, and *Chlaenius* sp.) prey on LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae in upland rice fields near Tanauan, Batangas, Philippines. The arboreal *Chlaenius* larvae (Fig. 1) actively search rice plants for LF larvae and were often found alone within folded leaves, presumably having consumed the LF.

In the headhouse, where predator and prey were caged at constant but variable densities, last-instar *C. posticalis* larvae exposed to 10 or more LF/cage became satiated at 1.3 last-instar LF larvae/d (Fig. 2).

LF population was highest in coconut-shaded rice fields, which in turn sustained higher carabid larval populations (see table). A more favorable prey:predator ratio occurred in sunny fields.

Chlaenius spp. did not prevent extensive leaf damage, but their activity reduced damage and population buildup. □

1. Adult and larva of *C. posticalis*, the most common species found in dryland rice fields of Batangas. The adults are ground dwellers and do not prey on LF.

2. Predation rate of *C. posticalis* larvae on LF. One carabid larva was held per cage with prey replaced daily over 1 wk, IRRRI headhouse.

Density dependent relationship of *Chlaenius* spp. ground beetle predators on host population in sunny and shaded upland rice fields^a, Tanauan, Batangas, Philippines.

Rice field	LF		Carabid predator (no. of larvae/m ²)	Prey:predator ratio
	Larvae (no./m ²)	Damaged leaves (%)		
Open	3.5 ± 2.3	65 ± 31	0.9 ± 0.9	3.9
Coconut shaded	9.8 ± 4.9	95 ± 40	1.9 ± 1.2	5.2

^a Av of 4 fields. Values are averages of 5 1-m² sample sizes (X ± SE) per field.

Rice water weevil host plants in Cuba

R. Meneses-Carbonell, Rice Experiment Station, Sur del Jibaro, Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba

Rice water weevil *Lissorhoptus brevisrostris* (Suffr.) is the most-difficult-to-control rice pest in Cuba because of its habits, adult longevity of up to 714 d, and host plant range.

L. brevisrostris lives in a variety of weeds on levees and in irrigation channels where weed control is difficult. If climatic conditions are unfavorable, as in Nov-Mar, the insect remains dormant on such weeds as *Brachiaria mutica*, but does not die, even without feeding for 205 d.

New records of rice water weevil host plants in Cuba, 1983.

Host plant
<i>Paspalum virgatum</i> L.
<i>Paspalum notatum</i> Fluegge
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.
<i>Panicum maximum</i> Jacq.
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.
<i>Leptochloa filiformis</i> Lam. (Beauv.)
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.
<i>Oryza latifolia</i> Desv.
<i>Cyperus odoratus</i> L.
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms

We sampled rice fields at Sur del Jibaro once a month to record *L. brevisrostris* hosts. Weeds with foliage damaged by *L. brevisrostris* were collected, and their roots were dissected to determine the presence of rice water weevil larvae and pupae.

In 1979, host plants of rice water weevil were reported; 16 were grasses, including *Paspalum distichum*, *B. mutica*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Leptochloa fascicularis*, and *Leptochloa* sp.

Other principal hosts were *Cyperus iria* and *C. esculentus*. Because the irrigation system in Sur del Jibaro uses dams, *Eichhornia paniculata* and *E. crassipes* also are important host plants.

Among the new *L. brevisrostris* host plants that we identified, graminaceous species were more abundant (see table). Both adults and larvae fed on those weeds. □

Accelerative effect of juvenoids and precocene-II on diapause breaking of the larvae of three stem borers (SB)

S. Chakravorty, M. K. Ghosh, and N. Roychoudhury, Entomology Laboratory, Zoology Department, University of Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal 741235, India

Larvae of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Chilo auricilius*, and *C. partellus* were collected

by incising the tillers of rice stubble in Dec to Feb 1982-83. Juvenoids hydroprene, methoprene, and precocene-II were applied topically in acetone dilutions at 1µl of the solution/larva. One µl pure acetone was applied in the control treatment. Larvae were reared in individual 5- × 0.5-cm glass tubes plugged with moist cotton and wrapped with black paper. The tubes were put inside a rearing chamber kept at 23 ± 1°C, 70-

80% relative humidity, and an 11-13 h lightdark cycle,

In the control treatment, *S. incertulas*, *C. auricilius*, and *C. partellus* moths developed in Feb-Mar, Feb, and Jun. In treated populations, moths developed earlier (see table), suggesting that these chemicals may accelerate diapause breaking of these stem borer larvae. The intensity of their effect may differ by species. □

Moth appearance from overwintering larvae treated topically with juvenoids and precocene-II, West Bengal, India.

Species	Dose ^a (µg/ individual)	Individuals (no.)		Moth appearance (%), 1982-83									
		Treated	Molted	Dec		Jan		Feb		Mar		Apr-May	Jun
				1-15	16-31	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-29	1-15	16-30	1-15	
<i>S. incertulas</i>	H 10	8	3	67	33								
	H 100	36	12	8	8	83							
	M 10	10	2	100									
	M 100	37	9	67	33								
	C	25	12					17	75	8			
<i>C. auricilius</i>	H 100	40	32		53	47							
	H 200	48	40		100								
	P 50	26	20		50	50							
	P 100	46	23		44	57							
	P 150	46	24		63	38							
	C	25	21				100						
<i>C. partellus</i>	H 100	30	20					60	25	15			
	H 200	35	20		14	86							
	P 50	10	7				71	29					
	C	10	10										100

^aH = hydroprene, M = methoprene, C = control, P = precocene-II.

Life cycle of *Marasmia patnalis*, a leaf folder (LF) of rice in the Philippines

R. C. Joshi, E. Baldos and E. A. Heinrichs Entomology Department, IRRI

From Oct to Mar 1984, caterpillars of *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) were observed folding and damaging rice leaves at IRRI. This LF species is widely distributed in Southeast Asia. However, it has escaped attention of rice entomologists because of superficial similarity to the more commonly known LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

We studied the life cycle and habits of *M. patnalis* in the greenhouse at 26-34°C

with 70-80% relative humidity. Gravid female moths collected from the field

Life cycle of LF *Marasmia Patnalis* reared on TN1 rice, IRRI, 1984.

Character	Duration ^a (d)		Survival (%)
	Range	Average	
Egg	4-5	4	92.3
Larva	21-25	23	88.0
Prepupa	1-2	1	- ^b
Pupa	7-11	9	74.0
Total development period	33-43	37	
Adult longevity			
Male	4-3	3	
Female	5-7	5	

^an = 60 males and 60 females. ^bNo data.